

Ec-A: A Task Allocation Algorithm for Energy Minimization in Multiprocessor Systems

Authors : Anju S. Pillai, T.B. Isha

Abstract : With the necessity of increased processing capacity with less energy consumption; power aware multiprocessor system has gained more attention in the recent future. One of the additional challenges that is to be solved in a multi-processor system when compared to uni-processor system is job allocation. This paper presents a novel task dependent job allocation algorithm: Energy centric- Allocation (Ec-A) and Rate Monotonic (RM) scheduling to minimize energy consumption in a multiprocessor system. A simulation analysis is carried out to verify the performance increase with reduction in energy consumption and required number of processors in the system.

Keywords : Energy consumption, Job allocation, Multiprocessor systems, Task dependent

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